

Lightweight Residual Networks with Ghost Blocks for Efficient Direction-of-Arrival Estimation

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Abstract—Accurate and computationally efficient direction-of-arrival (DoA) estimation remains a fundamental requirement in wireless communications, radar, and array signal processing. This paper presents novel residual network, a deep learning architecture that incorporates ghost blocks and squeeze-and-excitation (SE) modules into the ResNet framework to address the trade-off between accuracy and complexity. The introduction of ghost blocks reduces parameters and floating-point operations by approximately 50%, while SE modules improve feature discrimination with negligible overhead. Experimental evaluations demonstrate that the proposed architecture achieves high estimation accuracy, with F1 scores reaching 96.80% in single-signal scenarios and 89.21% with five simultaneous signals, alongside mean absolute errors between 0.016° and 0.161° . The proposed approach thus provides a balanced solution that combines precision with computational efficiency, supporting real-time deployment.

Index Terms—Direction of arrival (DoA) estimation, ghost module, lightweight deep learning, residual learning, squeeze and excitation (SE) blocks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Accurate direction-of-arrival (DoA) estimation of signals plays a pivotal role in advancing spatial signal processing research. The ability to localize multiple sources with high precision under realistic operating conditions is essential for the development of reliable communication and sensing systems. Despite the long-standing success of classical approaches—including subspace-based and maximum likelihood methods—their performance often deteriorates in adverse environments, including low signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs), highly correlated sources, and scenarios with limited computational resources. These challenges underscore the need for more robust and computationally efficient solutions, particularly as

future systems demand scalability, adaptability, and deployment on resource-constrained platforms.

In recent years, deep learning has emerged as a transformative paradigm for DoA estimation, offering data-driven alternatives that overcome several limitations of traditional approaches. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and other deep neural networks have demonstrated the ability to learn robust spatial and spectral features directly from data, yielding state-of-the-art results in diverse conditions [1], [2]. Residual networks (ResNets), have proven effective in capturing hierarchical representations and have been successfully applied to multi-signal DoA estimation when combined with attention mechanisms [3]. Furthermore, recent advances such as transformer-based architectures highlight the continued trend toward more powerful deep models for DoA tasks [4], [5]. Despite these successes, these methods typically impose high computational demands, presenting challenges for real-time and edge deployment where efficiency is as critical as accuracy.

Several attempts have been made to mitigate this trade-off between accuracy and complexity. Lightweight architectures, e.g., MobileNet [6], along with efficient residual network variants, have sought to reduce model parameters and floating-point operations while preserving predictive performance. Although these strategies achieve partial success, they often involve compromises. Either accuracy is sacrificed to minimize complexity, or excessive computational overhead is retained to maintain precision. This persistent imbalance underscores the need for architectures that achieve both high accuracy and low complexity, particularly in latency- and resource-constrained edge environments. Traditional low-complexity solutions in

the DoA literature, such as those focusing on mutual coupling and hardware-related constraints [7], address efficiency from a signal processing perspective but do not incorporate the advantages of deep learning. In contrast, GhostNet introduced a novel approach to reducing redundancy in CNNs by generating “ghost” feature maps through inexpensive linear operations, thereby mimicking standard convolutions at a fraction of the computational cost [8]. GhostNetV2 further extended this concept by incorporating long-range attention mechanisms to enhance representational capacity [9]. While ghost modules have been widely adopted in computer vision, their potential in spatial signal processing and DoA estimation remains largely unexplored.

This work addresses this gap by introducing a novel architecture that integrates ghost blocks into ResNet for DoA estimation. When combined with squeeze-and-excitation (SE) blocks, which serve as attention mechanisms, this design enhances feature selection at minimal additional cost. Despite its promise, GhostNet has not been systematically investigated for DoA estimation, leaving open the question of its effectiveness in spatial signal processing and its suitability for real-time or resource-limited applications. The proposed model achieves competitive accuracy while substantially reducing computational demands, making it suitable for edge deployment. Furthermore, the study provides a comprehensive analysis of the impact of ghost and SE blocks on performance, examines the balance between complexity and accuracy, and discusses the potential of this modular design to extend toward more complex and dynamic signal environments.

II. DESIGN AND ADVANTAGES OF GHOST MODULES

A. Ghost Module: Efficient Feature Generation

CNNs depend on computationally expensive convolution operations to construct expressive intermediate feature maps. Rather than relying exclusively on standard convolutions, GhostNet employs a two-stage strategy: (i) primary convolutions generate a small set of intrinsic feature maps, and (ii) cheap linear operations, such as depthwise convolutions, expand these intrinsic maps into a larger set of so-called ghost feature maps. Each ghost module therefore comprises:

- Primary Convolution: A conventional 1×1 or 3×3 convolution to extract intrinsic features.
- Cheap Operations: Lightweight transformations (e.g., depthwise convolutions) applied to intrinsic features to produce additional ghost feature maps.

Let the input feature map be $X \in \mathbb{R}^{c \times h \times w}$, where c denotes the number of input channels, and h and w represent the spatial height and width, respectively. A standard convolutional layer that produces n output feature maps with a kernel of size $k \times k$ can be expressed as:

$$Y = X * f + b, \quad (1)$$

where $f \in \mathbb{R}^{c \times k \times k \times n}$ represents the convolution kernel, $b \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the bias vector, and $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times h' \times w'}$ is the resulting output feature map, with h' and w' denoting the spatial dimensions after convolution (depending on padding and stride). The associated number of floating-point operations (FLOPs) required for this convolution is given by:

$$\text{FLOPs} = n \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot c \cdot k^2, \quad (2)$$

where each multiplication-addition in the convolution is counted as one FLOP. Given that many output feature maps are redundant or linearly correlated, the ghost module proposes to generate only m intrinsic feature maps via standard convolution:

$$Y_0 = X * f_0, \quad (3)$$

where $f_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{c \times k \times k \times m}$ and $m < n$. To reach the target dimensionality n , each intrinsic map $y_i^0 \in Y_0$ is expanded into s feature maps through cheap linear transformations $\Phi_{i,j}$:

$$y_{ij} = \Phi_{i,j}(y_i^0), \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, m, \quad j = 1, \dots, s. \quad (4)$$

Thus, the final output feature map becomes:

$$Y = [y_{11}, y_{12}, \dots, y_{ms}] \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times h' \times w'}. \quad (5)$$

Here, $\Phi_{i,j}$ includes depthwise convolutions or linear shifts. The last transformation $\Phi_{i,s}$ is often the identity function to preserve the original map.

B. Complexity

Let s be the number of ghost features generated per intrinsic map. To obtain $n = m \cdot s$ output maps, the ghost module involves one standard convolution to generate $m = \frac{n}{s}$ intrinsic features and $(s-1)$ cheap operations per intrinsic feature. The total FLOPs becomes:

$$\text{FLOPs}_{\text{ghost}} = \frac{n}{s} \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot c \cdot k^2 + \frac{n}{s} \cdot (s-1) \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot d^2, \quad (6)$$

where $d \times d$ is the kernel size of the cheap operation (e.g., $d = 3$). The theoretical speed-up ratio is:

$$r_s = \frac{n \cdot h' \cdot w' \cdot c \cdot k^2}{\text{FLOPs}_{\text{ghost}}} = \frac{c \cdot k^2}{\frac{1}{s} \cdot c \cdot k^2 + \frac{s-1}{s} \cdot d^2} \approx s. \quad (7)$$

The corresponding parameter compression ratio is:

$$r_c \approx s. \quad (8)$$

This approximation holds under the condition $s \ll c$, and when $d \approx k$, as is typical in GhostNet designs.

III. PROPOSED GHOST MODULE AUGMENTED RESNET ARCHITECTURE

This section introduces the proposed architecture, a computationally efficient adaptation of the ResNet-18 architecture that integrates ghost blocks for DoA estimation. The evaluation is conducted on a multi-signal DoA estimation task involving one to five simultaneously impinging signals at multiple SNR scenarios. The correlation matrix, computed from a 16-element uniform linear array, serves as the network input. After preprocessing, it is represented as a tensor of dimensions $16 \times 16 \times 3$, where the first two dimensions correspond to the structured spatial features and the third dimension captures multiple feature channels (e.g., real, imaginary, and phase components). The models are trained to predict among 121 discrete DoA classes, uniformly spanning from 30° to 150°

with a resolution of 1° . Furthermore, a comprehensive hyperparameter optimization strategy is employed to determine optimal configurations.

A. Proposed Architecture

Fig. 1: Proposed ResNet architecture, incorporating ghost modules and SE blocks.

The proposed architecture integrates ghost modules to enhance computational efficiency while preserving the feature extraction capabilities of ResNet-18. Inspired by [8], the ghost module splits convolution into two stages: a primary convolution and a cheap operation. The primary convolution is a pointwise convolution to generate a reduced set of feature maps, defined as $c_{\text{init}} = \lceil c_{\text{out}}/r \rceil$, where c_{out} is the desired output channels and $r = 2$ is the reduction ratio. The cheap operation employs a depthwise convolution with kernel sizes of 3, 5, or 7 to produce additional feature maps, which are concatenated with the primary outputs and truncated to c_{out} channels. This approach reduces parameters and FLOPs by approximately 50% compared to standard convolutions by exploiting feature redundancy.

The ghost residual block combines two ghost modules within a residual learning framework. The first ghost module processes the input, optionally with a stride (1, 2, or 3) for spatial downsampling, followed by a second ghost Module with stride 1. For cases with a stride value of 2, a depthwise convolution and batch normalization ensure spatial compatibility. In Stage 3, SE blocks are included to recalibrate channel-wise features using global average pooling, a reduction convolution (to $c_{\text{out}}/4$), ReLU activation, an expansion convolution, and a sigmoid function to produce channel weights. These SE blocks enhance feature selection, improving robustness in noisy conditions. Stages 1 and 2 do not include SE blocks, relying solely on ghost modules and residual connections. A shortcut connection, with a 1×1 convolution for dimension matching if needed, preserves residual learning, enhancing gradient flow and training stability. Stage 3 consists of three Ghost Residual Blocks, which expand the number of channels from 256 to 512. The first block applies a stride of 2, while all blocks integrate SE modules. After this stage, the resulting feature maps have approximate spatial dimensions of 2×2 . The output stage applies adaptive average pooling to reduce the feature maps to a size of $1 \times 1 \times 512$. This is followed by a fully connected sequence with layer dimensions $512 \rightarrow 1024 \rightarrow 512 \rightarrow 121$. Dropout is applied across the layers with rates of 0.3, 0.2, and 0.1, which can be configured to alternative values of 0.1, 0.3, or 0.5. The final layer produces probability distributions over 121 discrete angle classes. A diagram of the proposed model is presented in Fig. 1

Each SE block in the three ghost Residual Blocks of Stage 3 operates on feature maps with 512 channels, applying the following steps:

- **Squeeze:** Global average pooling reduces the spatial dimensions (approximately 2×2) to 1×1 , producing a channel-wise descriptor of size $1 \times 1 \times 512$.
- **Excitation:** A sequence of two 1×1 convolutions: the first reduces the channel count to 128 ($512/4$), followed by ReLU activation; the second restores the channel count to 512, followed by a sigmoid activation to produce channel-wise weights within the interval $[0, 1]$.
- **Scaling:** The weights are multiplied element-wise with the input feature maps, recalibrating channel importance to emphasize relevant features for angle prediction.

B. Hyperparameter Tuning

The model is optimized through a two-phase hyperparameter tuning process to identify the best configurations for each signal number (1 to 5) at 0 dB SNR, as summarized in Table I. The process first optimizes the architecture by tuning kernel size, channel scale, and regularizer rate, then fine-tunes the dropout rate for the best architecture per signal number.

In the first phase, a grid search was conducted over kernel sizes (3, 5, 7), channel scales (strides: 1, 2, 3), and regularizer rates (0.0, 0.0001, 0.001), with a fixed learning rate of 0.001 and dropout rate of 0.3. The model was trained on $16 \times 16 \times 3$ input, evaluating performance using validation F1 score. The configuration yielding the highest F1 score was selected. For instance, kernel size 7 for 4 signals captures broader spatial patterns, while channel scale 1 preserves resolution for the small input.

Fig. 2: MAE Comparison between the proposed ResNet and a CNN for different numbers of signals and SNR levels.

TABLE I: Optimized configurations for each signal at 0 dB SNR.

Signals	Kernel Size	Channel Scale	Dropout Rate	Reg. Rate
1	3	1	0.1	0.0001
2	5	1	0.1	0.0
3	5	1	0.1	0.001
4	7	1	0.3	0.0001
5	3	1	0.1	0.0001

In the second phase, the dropout rate was fine-tuned (0.1, 0.3, 0.5) for the best architecture per signal number, keeping other parameters fixed. A dropout rate of 0.1 was optimal for 1, 2, 3, and 5 signals, while 0.3 was preferred for 4 signals, addressing increased complexity.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Mean Angular Error and F1 Score

The baseline CNN model is designed as a deep architecture without residual connections or ghost modules. It begins with an initial 5×5 convolution producing 64 channels, followed by batch normalization and ReLU activation, while preserving the 16×16 spatial resolution. Layer 1 consists of two blocks, each comprising two 3×3 convolutions with 64 channels, batch normalization, and ReLU, maintaining the same dimensions. In layer 2, the first block applies a 3×3 convolution with stride 2, expanding the channel size to 128 and reducing the resolution to 8×8 , followed by another 3×3 convolution with stride 1. Similarly, layer 3 includes two blocks, the first using a 3×3 convolution with stride 2 to increase the channel size to

256 and reduce the resolution to 4×4 , followed by another 3×3 convolution. The network concludes with adaptive average pooling, producing a $1 \times 1 \times 256$ output, which is passed through a fully connected sequence of layers (256–512–121) with a dropout rate of 0.3 for regularization.

In contrast, the proposed ResNet incorporates residual connections and ghost modules, which differentiate it from the purely sequential structure of the CNN. The use of residual connections alleviates the vanishing gradient problem and allows for deeper architectures (10 residual blocks compared to 7 convolutional layers in the baseline). Furthermore, ghost modules reduce the number of parameters and floating-point operations, whereas a CNN relies entirely on standard convolutions, increasing computational complexity. Finally, SE blocks are integrated into stage 3 to enhance feature selection, providing an additional mechanism absent in the uniform processing structure of a CNN. For 1 signal, the proposed model achieves an F1 score of 96.80% and MAE of 0.016° , and for 5 signals, 89.21% and 0.161° . The standard CNN yields lower F1 scores and higher MAE, particularly for higher signal counts, due to its lack of residual connections and feature recalibration, as detailed in Table II and Figs. 2 and 3.

B. Computational Complexity

The SE blocks add minimal computational overhead. For each block, the squeeze operation (global average pooling) has negligible FLOPs, while the excitation step involves two 1×1 convolutions: one with 512×128 parameters (65,536) and another with 128×512 parameters (65,536), totaling 131,072

TABLE II: F1 Score (%) comparison between proposed ResNet and a CNN.

Signals	SNR (dB)	Proposed ResNet	CNN
1	-20	95.9533	89.2934
	0	96.8037	93.4848
	20	98.2130	96.1297
2	-20	88.2561	82.0939
	0	94.4857	88.9494
	20	94.5811	92.5811
3	-20	89.3669	81.0709
	0	89.4155	85.8984
	20	90.2720	87.8935
4	-20	83.1190	76.8867
	0	89.8249	82.3431
	20	90.9076	86.2518
5	-20	82.3577	74.674
	0	89.2124	78.405
	20	89.4271	82.6685

Fig. 3: Mean angular error (MAE) comparison with 3 incoming signals across different SNR values.

parameters per SE block. With three SE blocks in Stage 3, this adds 0.39M parameters, a small fraction compared to the millions of parameters in the convolutional layers. The FLOPs for SE blocks are similarly low, as 1x1 convolutions are computationally efficient. This ensures that our model remains lightweight compared to a standard ResNet, even with SE blocks, maintaining suitability for resource-constrained environments.

In the context of DoA estimation, SE blocks are particularly effective in Stage 3, where feature maps are spatially compact (2x2) and channel-rich (512). Low SNR introduces noise that can obscure angle-specific features, but SE blocks enhance the model's focus on channels corresponding to dominant signal patterns, improving prediction accuracy for multiple signals (up to 5). The higher F1 score for 4 signals (89.82%) with a larger kernel size (7) suggests that SE blocks complement the broader receptive fields by refining channel-wise attention, enabling precise angle discrimination.

V. CONCLUSION

This work introduced a novel and efficient solution for DoA estimation, demonstrating that the integration of ghost blocks into the ResNet architecture offers substantial improvements in both accuracy and computational efficiency. The experimental

results highlight the potential to maintain high estimation accuracy, even under challenging signal conditions, while significantly reducing the number of parameters and floating-point operations. Moreover, the incorporation of SE blocks further enhances feature discrimination with minimal computational overhead, thereby making the model highly suitable for edge deployment. Beyond these results, the modularity of the proposed framework supports adaptability to more complex scenarios, including higher signal counts, variable signal-to-noise ratios, and non-uniform array geometries. This flexibility positions the proposed model as a promising foundation for future research and development in real-time and resource-constrained DoA estimation systems. Ultimately, the presented findings establish a clear pathway for extending deep learning architectures toward scalable, efficient, and high-performance solutions in array signal processing.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Abdullah, M. S. Li, J. He, K. Wang, C. Fumeaux and W. Withayachumnankul, “Direction of Arrival Estimation in Terahertz Communications using Convolutional Neural Networks,” 2024 49th International Conference on Infrared, Millimeter, and Terahertz Waves (IRMMW-THz), Perth, Australia, 2024, pp. 1-2, doi: 10.1109/IRMMW-THz60956.2024.10697592.
- [2] Y. Xu, H. Guo, R. Fan, C. Si and X. Ding, “An Intelligent Direction Finding Method with Deep Neural Network,” 2020 IEEE 2nd International Conference on Civil Aviation Safety and Information Technology (ICCASIT, Weihai, China, 2020, pp. 1094-1098, doi: 10.1109/ICCA-SIT50869.2020.9368549.
- [3] Long Wu, Yue Fu, Xu Yang, Lu Xu, Shuyu Chen, Yong Zhang, Jianlong Zhang, “Research on the multi-signal DOA estimation based on ResNet with the attention module combined with beamforming (RAB-DOA),” Applied Acoustics, Volume 231, 2025, 110541, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2025.110541>.
- [4] S. Ye, Y. Xu, K. Qian and X. Wang, “A Transformer Approach to Two-Dimensional DOA Estimation of Coherent Signals,” 2025 5th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Industrial Technology Applications (AIITA), Xi’an, China, 2025, pp. 699-704, doi: 10.1109/AIITA65135.2025.11048093.
- [5] C. M. Mylonakis, P. Velanas and Z. D. Zaharis, “On the Implementation of Temporal Fusion Transformers for Target Recognition and Tracking,” 2025 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC), Milan, Italy, 2025, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/WCNC61545.2025.10978748.
- [6] Howard, A. G., Zhu, M., Chen, B., Kalenichenko, D., Wang, W., Weyand, T., ... & Adam, H. (2017), “Mobilenets: Efficient convolutional neural networks for mobile vision applications”, arXiv preprint arXiv:1704.04861.
- [7] Y. Zhang, W. Cui, H. Xu, J. Zhang, X. Li and P. Zhang, “Low-complexity Direction-of-arrival Estimation of Coprime Array based on Noise Subspace Reconstruction,” 2019 IEEE 8th Joint International Information Technology and Artificial Intelligence Conference (ITAIC), Chongqing, China, 2019, pp. 108-113, doi: 10.1109/ITAIC.2019.8785613.
- [8] Han, K., Wang, Y., Tian, Q., Guo, J., Xu, C., & Xu, C. (2020). “GhostNet: More features from cheap operations”, Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 1580- 1589.
- [9] Tang, Y., Han, K., Guo, J., Xu, C., Li, Y., Xu, C., & Wang, Y. (2022). “GhostNetV2: Enhance cheap operation with long-range attention”, Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, 35, 9969-9982.